

Attitude of Secondary School Teachers Towards the Teaching of Sex Education in Secondary School in Aguata Local Government Area of Anambra State

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Abstract

The study investigated the attitude of secondary school teachers towards the teaching of sex education secondary school in Aguata Local Government Area of Anambra state. Four null hypotheses was tested at 0.05 level of significance. The design of this study was a descriptive survey. The population comprises all the eight hundred and twenty four (824) secondary school teachers in Agutua local government area in Anambra state. The sample for this study is 120 secondary school teachers in Aguata local government area. 12 teachers were selected from 10 secondary schools in Aguata local government area using simple random sampling technique by balloting with replacement. The instrument for data collection is a structured questionnaire developed by the researcher titled “ Teachers Attitude Towards the Teaching of Sex Education Questionnaire(TATETSEQ). Which sought to elicit information on the teachers attitude towards teaching sex education in secondary schools. The questionnaire is divided into two part A and B. Part A contain data information such as gender of the teachers, working experience, educational qualification and marital status, while part B contain twenty items based on the four research questions. The instrument has a reliability of 0.76 which was obtain using test –retest. From the analysis the following findings were made: There is a significant difference between the attitude of male teachers and female teachers towards the teaching of sex education in secondary schools, There is a significant difference between the attitude of experience teachers and in-experience teachers towards the teaching of sex education in secondary schools and There is no significant difference between the attitude of graduate teachers and non- graduate teachers towards the teaching of sex education in secondary schools. recommendation was made that The teaching of sex education should be encouraged at all levels of education especially at the secondary school level and The teaching of sex education should be regarded as an important form of social service in the community or society at large.

Key words: Attitude, Secondary School Teachers, Sex Education

Introduction

The most significant and notable characteristic of human thought and behaviour is the tendency to exhibit some form of attitude toward self, object, issues and situations. Meanwhile, teacher attitude or behaviour act as greater encouragement for students performance in school.

According to Abaggara (2009), students tend to imitate and internalised a great deal of teachers behaviour. Teachers who are happy with the teaching profession show more interest and produce student who are to achieve greater academic excellence.

In this view, if the attitude of a teacher toward the teaching of some certain topic is positive, the students will pay more attention to it. But in a situation whereby the teacher makes the students to understand that they merely waste their time in acquiring academic knowledge and skills, students will see no usefulness in paying attention/ to achieve the actual knowledge which is required of them. Therefore, the attitude of teachers serve influence the students behaviour toward their goal in life. Attitude in this sense means the interest which the teacher has toward the subject in question.

According to Brodenck and Bernard (2011), sex education is an education which gives rooms to the set of constructive attentive to the values, ideas and information about sex. It's also viewed as the acquisition of knowledge that guide human sexuality. The rapid increase of the growth in early sexual activities among teenagers brings forth early marriage and pregnancies, which could be out of ignorance on the part of the teenagers/ adolescents. Sex education is very essential, hence it guide against pre-martial pregnancy. Furthermore, the knowledge acquired from sex education will help the students to know or have knowledge of sexually transmitted disease, prevention as well as pre martial pregnancy. This is because the presentation of the teacher can motivate the students to understand the subject matter.

The method as well as the approach to teaching sex education will be felt by the students and they will see everything in their proper context as means to an end instead of an end to themselves. At school, students are taught to be of good behaviour which will help them to be capable of not only impacting knowledge but also shoulder responsibilities, showing initiative and assist those in need. In discussing the attitude of teachers, the quality of the teacher should not be left out. This is because he/she must acquire certain qualities before he will be able to give correct information. In this regard, the quality of the teacher prove his/her attitude. The thing that remain in the children memory after the lesson might have been taught or learnt by the teachers. Sex education is one of the most important educational needs of adolescents as noted by Cairms, Collins and Hiebert (2014). However, sex education is often a controversial topic which perhaps on the other subject (apart form evolution) has sparking as much debate in the society. Sex education has always been and will probably be an emotional topic. Considering the importance of the issues it deal with, considering the intimate nature of the subject, considering have tightly bound sexual more are to the majority of people's concepts of good, bad and their own self image. Teenagers are exposed to culture that uses sex and sexual imagery to everything. The consequence for early pregnancy are therefore so much greater now than ever.

Though there is need to educates students in secondary school on sex education, parents oppose such educational program due to the fear that imparting sex education would lead to experimentation with sex. And as noted by Adeyemo (2014) some parents felt that raising such issues might encourage undesirable behaviour by the youths. While on the other hand Sathe (2011) in his study found out that most teachers have positive attitude towards the need for sex

education is necessary for teenagers in today's world but some may argue that public schools are not good at teaching sex education.

Attitude as a concept has been defined by various authors Okpala (2011) see attitude as a predisposition to respond to an object rather than the actual behaviour toward such an object. Attitude therefore is concerned with one readiness to exhibits behaviour and not the behaviour itself. Adeyongju (2008) see attitude as the predisposition to act in a positive or negative way towards person, objects, ideals and events. On the part of Abiri (2010) attitude is defined as an acquired tendency to react, covertly or overtly in manner, which expresses certain danger of favourability or unfavourability in relation to the environment.

Religion plays an important role in individual sexuality as its principles, regulations and practice affect our everyday interaction. Wilson and Filsgar (2014) emphasised that religious beliefs influence sexual attitudes and behaviours. Also, Asekun, Fawole, Dairo, & Amusan, (2013) opined that religions and spiritual belief influence feeling about morality, sexual behaviour, pre-martial sexual behavioural, adultery, divorce contraception and abortion.

According to Lauman (2014), conservation or traditional beliefs exerts strong impact on sexual experiences for Razi (2013), noted Islam endorse any form of beneficial knowledge which must be acquired by every muslim male and female and also recognised the dynamic of change in human societies as long as the reason is not placed at far or as above divine wisdom. Teachers attitude toward sex education in our present day society have caused or lead to serious sex problem sex problem, such as teenage pregnancies, abortion, and so no. Sex education is a controversial topic, with perhaps no other subject (apart from education) sparking as much debate. Teachers and indeed school administrators have identified fear of parental/ community opposition as major barriers to the provision of sex education.

Statement of the Problem

During the past century, there has been as acceleration in the rate of physical growth of children and adolescents, leading to faster and earlier maturation. However, it seem that neither parent nor schools have made any effort to respond to these changes. In the United Kingdom, there is no requirement to teach sex education in primary school. Some school provide information the year before pupils leave the secondary schools when the children are eleven years old. In some instances, information is directed only at girls and the boys are left out of the discussion. Within the families, boys tend to receive less information about sex than girls. Among boy, this may result in the attitude that girls are responsible for birth control.

This is where sex education arises to put an end to this ugly situation. Sex education should be introduced into secondary schools as a subject in the school curriculum, to properly teach how to behave about sex (resi & Seidl, 2013). Scales and Kirly (2014) opined that teacher in fact opposed to school based sex education. The study therefore tried to answer the questions, what is the attitudes of teachers toward the teaching of sex education as a subject in secondary school.

Purpose of the Study

The main purpose of the study is to investigate the attitude of secondary school teachers towards the teaching of sex education as a subject in secondary school.

Specially the study seek to

1. Investigate the attitude of male and female teachers towards the teaching of sex education in secondary schools
2. Ascertain the attitude of experience teachers and in-experience teachers towards the teaching of sex education in secondary schools
3. Investigate the attitude of graduate teachers and non graduate teachers towards the teaching of sex education in secondary schools

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significant.

1. There is no significant difference in the attitude of male and female teachers towards the teaching of sex education in secondary schools.
2. There is no significant difference in the attitude of experience teachers and in-experience teachers towards the teaching of sex education in secondary schools?
3. There is no significant difference in the attitude of graduate teachers and non-graduate teachers towards the teaching of sex education in secondary schools?

METHOD

Design of the study

The design of this study was a descriptive survey. The researcher adopted a survey design to investigate teachers attitude towards the teaching of sex education as a subject in secondary schools in Aguata Local Government area of Anambra state.

Population of the study

In this research study, the population comprises of all the eight hundred and twenty four (824) secondary schools in Aguata local government area in Anambra state.

Sample and Sampling Techniques

The sample for this study is 120 secondary school teachers in Aguata local government area. 12 teacher were selected using simple random sampling technique by balloting with replacement from 10 secondary schools in Aguata local government area.

Instrument of data collection

The instrument for data collection is a structured questionnaire developed by the researcher titled “ Teachers Attitude Towards the Teaching of Sex Education Questionnaire(TATETSEQ). Which sought to elicit information on the teachers attitude towards teaching sex education in secondary schools. The questionnaire is divided into two part A and B. Part A contain data information such as gender of the teachers, working experience, educational qualification and marital status, while part B contain twenty items based on the four research questions on a five point likert scale ranging from Strongly Agree (SA), Agree (A), Un-decided (UD), Disagree (D), and Strongly Disagree (SD).

The respondents were required to tick (✓) on any of the item they deem most suitable to describe teachers attitude towards the teaching of sex education as a subject in secondary schools.

Reliability of instrument

The instrument has a reliability of 0.76 which was obtain using test –retest. That is twenty copies of the questionnaire were administered to teacher outside the local government area of the study and in another two weeks time the same copies of questionnaires were re-administered to

the same teachers, at this time of administration the questionnaire were reshuffled(see appendix A)

Method of Data Collection

A total of one hundred and twenty copies of questionnaire were administered in the selected secondary schools. The direct delivery techniques (DDT) was used to administered the questionnaire of the study. This mean that the researcher paid a direct visit to the school and administered the questionnaire himself and collected them back accordingly. This ensured one hundred percent return rare.

Method of Data Analysis

Data was analyzed item by item mean and standard deviation (SD) were calculated for each of the items in order to find out the variations, disparity in opinion, or how homogenous or heterogeneous the opinion of the principals were to each of the items. The T-test statistics was used to test the null hypotheses formulated at 0.05 level of significance. For decision, any item that scored a mean of 3.0 and above was regarded as accepted while items that score mean value below 3.0 were regarded as de-accepted .

Result

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant difference in the attitude of male and female teachers towards the teaching of sex education in secondary schools.

Answer to Hypothesis one is Shown In Table 1

Table 1: T-test analysis of the attitude of male teachers and female teachers towards the teaching of sex education in secondary schools.

Variable	N	X	SD	DF	T-val	T-Crit	Decision	Level of Significance
Male	58	44.26	9.52	118	4.517	1.96	significant (Rejected)	0.05
Female	62	38.15	8.74					

Table 1, shows that 58 male teachers had a mean (X) of 44.26 with standard deviation 9.52 while 62 female teachers had a mean (X) of 38.15 with standard deviation of 8.74. The table shows that the t-calculated value of 4.517 was higher than the t-critical value of 1.96. Hence the null hypothesis was rejected. This shows that there was significant different between attitude of male teachers and female teachers towards the teaching of sex education in secondary schools.

Hypothesis 2: There is no significant difference in the attitude of experience teachers and in-experience teachers towards the teaching of sex education in secondary schools

Answer to Hypothesis 2 is Shown In Table 2

Table 2: T-test analysis the attitude of experience teachers and in-experience teachers towards the teaching of sex education in secondary schools.

Variable	N	X	SD	DF	T-val	T-Crit	Decision	Level of Significance
Experience teachers	50	33.32	5.55	118	6.156	1.96	significant (Rejected)	0.05
In-experience teachers	70	27.69	6.84					

In table 2, shows that 50 experience teachers had a mean (X) of 33.32 with standard deviation 5.55 while 70 in-experience teachers had a mean (X) of 27.69 with standard deviation of 6.84. The table also shows that the t-calculated value of 6.156 was higher than the t-critical value of 1.96. Hence the null hypothesis was rejected. This implies that there was a significant difference between the attitude of experience teachers and in-experience teachers towards the teaching of sex education in secondary schools.

Hypothesis 3: There is no significant difference in the attitude of graduate teachers and non-graduate teachers towards the teaching of sex education in secondary schools

Answer to Hypothesis three is Shown In Table 3

Table 3: T-test analysis of the attitude of graduate teachers and non-graduate teachers towards the teaching of sex education in secondary schools.

Variable	N	X	SD	DF	T-val	T-Crit	Decision	Level of Significance
Graduate teacher	55	35.23	6.31	118	0.515	1.96	Not Significant (Accepted)	0.05
Non-Graduate teacher	65	34.68	8.11					

The result in table 3, shows that 55 of graduate teachers has a mean of 35.23 with standard deviation of 6.31. While 65 non of graduate teachers had a mean of 34.68 with standard deviation of 8.11. The table also shows that the t-calculated value of 0.515 was less than the t-critical value of 1.96. Hence, the null hypothesis was accepted. This indicates that there was no significant difference between the the attitude of graduate teachers and non-graduate teachers towards the teaching of sex education in secondary schools.

Discussion

The purpose of this study is to investigate the attitude of secondary school teachers towards the teaching of sex education as a subject in secondary school. The results of the study that emerged could be considered significant assessment of the attitude of secondary school teachers towards the teaching of sex education as a subject in secondary school in Aguata t Local Government Area of Anambra state. The first finding of this study shows, both male and female teachers differ in their attitude toward the teaching of sex education in secondary schools. The findings of this study agree with Jose (2015) who argue that female teacher are at the forefront of championing

the teaching of sex education as a subject in secondary schools. Uche (2015) also agreed with the finding that female teachers feel more comfortable discussing sex education with students than the male counterpart. This finding contradicted the work of Agu (2011), who posit that male and female teachers do not differ in the attitude toward sex education. The findings also revealed that there was a significant difference between the attitude of male teachers and female teachers towards the teaching of sex education in secondary schools.

Findings from the second research questions pointed out that both experience teachers and in-experience teachers differ in their attitude towards the teaching of sex education as subject in secondary schools. This find oppose the work of Conte (2013), who posit that the teaching years of experience of teachers do no count in their attitude toward the inclusion of sex education as a subject in senior secondary schools. The finding tend to tally with Abubakar (2015), who vehemently said that experience of teacher in teacher in their attitude toward the teaching of sex education as subject is pre-requisite for effective handling of sexuality matter among secondary school students in Nigeria. The hypothesis revealed that there is a significant difference between the attitude of experience teachers and in-experience teachers towards the teaching of sex education in secondary schools.

More so, research question three revealed that both of graduate teachers and non graduate teachers differ in their attitude towards the teaching of sex education as a subject in secondary schools. This findings agreed with Bush (2011), who said the quality of sex education programme offer to secondary school students is a functionality of the education qualification of the teachers and various course the teachers have undertaken at the graduate and post graduate level regarding sex education as a subject to be taught to adolescents. Also, Dame (2009) affirm this finding that a teacher who has not taken course at university level in sexuality education is not competent to teach sex education to students. The hypothesis also revealed that There is no significant difference between the attitude of graduate teachers and non- graduate teachers towards the teaching of sex education in secondary schools.

Lastly, findings form research questions four pointed out that, both married teachers and single teachers differ in their attitude towards the teaching of sex education as a subject in secondary schools. This finding agreed with Jose (2011), who posited that married teacher are at better advantage in teaching sex education because of the cultural and religion negative view point on sex to be taught by unmarried person.

Conclusion

Based on the findings of the study, the following conclusion were made:

- Genders of teachers differ in their attitude toward the teaching of sex education in secondary schools.
- Experience of teachers differ in their attitude towards the teaching of sex education as subject in secondary schools.
- Educational qualification of teachers Both differ in their attitude towards the teaching of sex education as a subject in secondary schools.
- Marital status of teachers differ in their attitude towards the teaching of sex education as a subject in secondary schools.

- There is a significant difference between the attitude of male teachers and female teachers towards the teaching of sex education in secondary schools.
- There is a significant difference between the attitude of experience teachers and in-experience teachers towards the teaching of sex education in secondary schools.
- There is no significant difference between the attitude of graduate teachers and non-graduate teachers towards the teaching of sex education in secondary schools.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the researcher proffers the following recommendations were made:

1. The teaching of sex education should be encouraged at all levels of education especially at the secondary school level.
2. The teaching of sex education should be regarded as an important form of social service in the community or society at large.
3. Sex education should be used as a means or opportunity for proper counseling in secondary schools.

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